

1 **Design of active electrospun mats with single and core-shell structures to achieve**
2 **different curcumin release kinetics**

3

4 Adrián Rojas, Eliezer Velásquez, Luan Garrido, María José Galotto, Carol López de
5 Dicastillo*

6

7 Laboratory of Food Packaging (LABEN). University of Santiago de Chile (USACH).
8 Technology Faculty. CEDENNA. Center for the Development of Nanoscience and
9 Nanotechnology

10

11 **ABSTRACT**

12 In this work, core-shell electrospun mats based on poly (lactic acid) (PLA) and polyvinyl alcohol
13 (PVA) were developed as novel curcumin release materials. The effect of the incorporation of
14 cellulose nanocrystals (CNN) in the PLA shell structure on structural, thermal and curcumin release
15 were studied. A phenomenological mass transfer model was used to correlate the experimental release
16 kinetic data as well as the structural and thermal characterization of the electrospun mats. Curcumin
17 distribution coefficients ($K_{P/SA}$) values for core-shell electrospun PLA/PVA mats were higher
18 than $K_{P/SA}$ values of uniaxial active PLA. Modelling analysis evidenced PLA/PVA coaxial
19 structures slowed down the effective diffusion coefficients of curcumin, and this value
20 notoriously decreased by the incorporation of CNC in the PLA shell matrix due to the
21 tortuous path created through the PLA matrix.

22

23 **Keywords:** Coaxial electrospinning, poly (lactic acid), polyvinyl alcohol, curcumin,
24 cellulose nanocrystals, release kinetic

25 **1. Introduction**

26

27 The interest in controlled release technologies of active compounds in cosmetic,
28 pharmaceutical, active packaging and/or medical applications has greatly increased over last
29 years (Ezhilarasi, Karthik, Chhanwal, & Anandharamakrishnan, 2013; Torres-Martinez,
30 Cornejo Bravo, Serrano Medina, Pérez González, & Villarreal Gómez, 2018; Yam & Zhu,
31 2012). Specifically, active packaging is an innovative technology where antioxidants or
32 antimicrobials can be incorporated in packaging materials to be released to the food in order
33 to extend their shelf life (Chen, Lee, Zhu, & Yam, 2012; Gómez-Estaca, López-de-Dicastillo,
34 Hernández-Muñoz, Catalá, & Gavara, 2014; López de Dicastillo, Bustos, et al., 2017). Over
35 last years, electrospinning has emerged as a promising technique to encapsulate active
36 substances and achieve a sustainable release effectiveness (Quiles-Carrillo, Montanes,
37 Lagaron, Balart, & Torres-Giner, 2019; Wang et al., 2017). Electrospinning is characterized
38 by its simplicity and versatility to produce fibers with high surface-to-volume ratio and
39 porosity (Jacobsen, García-Moreno, Mendes, Mateiu, & Chronakis, 2018; Wen, Zong,
40 Linhardt, Feng, & Wu, 2017). A typical electrospinning system consists of a high-voltage
41 power supply, a syringe pump with a metal needle, and a grounded collector. An electric field
42 is applied between the needle tip and the grounded collector and distorts the hemispherical
43 surface of a droplet into a conical shape through the action of electrostatic forces. When the
44 applied electrical force overcomes the critical surface tension of the polymer liquid, an
45 electrically charged jet of the polymer is ejected and deposited on the collector as a randomly
46 oriented nonwoven mat of fibers ranging from micrometers to nanometers in diameter.
47 Electrospinning is an industry-viable process that allows to obtain high ratio of
48 length/diameter in a continuous process with controllable morphology and component

49 (López de Dicastillo, Roa, Garrido, Pereira, & Galotto, 2017; Yildiz, Celebioglu, Kilic,
50 Durgun, & Uyar, 2018; Zhang, Kang, Tarascon, & Kim, 2016). Nevertheless, some studies
51 have revealed conventional electrospun active mats present burst release of encapsulated
52 compounds due to the deposition of the active components on or near the surface of the fibers
53 (Yang et al., 2008; Zeng et al., 2005). Thus, the latest developments have introduced the
54 development of core-shell structures by using a coaxial needle with the main purpose of
55 controlling the release of active compounds. The coaxial emitter can develop concentric
56 bilayer fibrillar structures composed by polymers with different properties. This technique
57 has several advantages such as the possibility to electrospun nanofibers from non-spinnable
58 solutions, protecting sensitive active agents and controlling the release of active agents in a
59 more efficient way due to the presence of shell acting as an additional layer. The coaxial
60 electrospinning system has been studied in many areas such as the pharmaceutical,
61 electronics and biomedicine for tissue engineering (Aytac & Uyar, 2017; Gong, Wei, Ruan,
62 & Shen, 2019; Johnson, Ding, Nagiah, Monnet, & Tan, 2019; Zhang et al., 2016).

63 In this work, the main objective was achieving different release rates of curcumin, as a
64 model active agent with antimicrobial/antioxidant capacities, through the design of active
65 fibers by using uniaxial and core-shell electrospun structures. Coaxial electrospun structures
66 were composed by poly (lactic acid) (PLA) and polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) polymers at shell
67 and core structures respectively, due to their different polarities and properties. PLA is a
68 synthetic thermoplastic biopolymer that has attracted considerable attention in biomedical
69 and packaging applications owing to its excellent biodegradability and non-toxicity
70 (Casasola, Thomas, Trybala, & Georgiadou, 2014). Electrospun PLA nanofibers have been
71 designed with different purposes, and over last years, the encapsulation of sensitive bioactive
72 compounds have attracted special attention (Alazab, Mitchell, Davis, & Mohan, 2017; Vega-

73 Lugo & Lim, 2009). On the other hand, PVA is a hydrophilic polymer, water soluble, non-
74 toxic, biocompatible and biodegradable polymer that can be used in a wide range of
75 applications in medical, cosmetic, food, pharmaceutical, and packaging industries (Koski,
76 Yim, & Shivkumar, 2004; Shehata, Gaballah, Samir, Hamed, & Saad, 2016). On the other
77 hand, some works have evidenced the incorporation of nanofillers can modify release kinetic
78 parameters of active materials (Alvarado et al., 2018; Fortunati, Peltzer, Armentano,
79 Jiménez, & Kenny, 2013; Torres et al., 2014). Thus, the incorporation of cellulose
80 nanocrystals in the shell structure was also proposed with the intention of studying the effect
81 of this nanofiller on the curcumin release rate. The interest for cellulose nanocrystals has
82 increased over last decades due to their excellent characteristics such as a highly crystalline
83 structure, low density, biodegradability, transparency and high specific area (Manepalli &
84 Alavi, 2019; Martínez-Sanz, Lopez-Rubio, & Lagaron, 2013; Qian, Sheng, Yu, Xu, &
85 Fontanillo Lopez, 2018).

86

87 **2. Materials and Chemicals**

88

89 *2.1. Materials*

90

91 Poly (lactic acid) (PLA), 2003D (specific gravity $\frac{1}{4}$ 1.24; MFR g/10min (210 °C, 2.16
92 kg)), was purchased in pellet form from Natureworks® Co., Minnetonka (USA). Gohsenol
93 type AH-17 polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) (saponification degree 97-98.5% and viscosity 25-30
94 mPa.s) was obtained from The Nippon Synthetic Chemical Co. (Osaka, Japan). Curcumin
95 (Cur) (> 65%) was supplied by Sigma Aldrich® Chemistry. Cellulose nanocrystals (CNC)

96 were purchased from University of Maine. Chloroform, ethanol and dimethyl formamide
97 were supplied by Merck.

98

99 *2.2. Electrospinning*

100

101 Three active electrospun fibers containing curcumin were processed: core-shell structures
102 through coaxial electrospinning (1) PLA/PVA-Cur and (2) PLA.CNC/PVA-Cur, and
103 uniaxial structural mat (3) PLA-Cur. Electrospun mats PLA, PVA, PLA-Cur and PVA-Cur
104 were also developed to understand structural and thermal properties.

105

106 *2.2.1. Preparation of solutions for electrospinning*

107 Poly (lactic acid) (PLA) solutions at 10% (w/v) were prepared under
108 chloroform/dimethylformamide (CHCl₃/DMF) with a ratio of 7/3. Polymeric solutions were
109 stirred at room temperature for 2 h. DMF was used to increase the solution conductivity and
110 dielectric constant (Tsuji, 2013). PLA solutions included: a) control PLA; b) PLA-Cur: PLA
111 with curcumin at 1.23% (w/w) respect to polymer weight; and c) PLA.CNC: PLA with
112 cellulose nanocrystals at 2.5% (w/w) respect to polymer weight. Core-structure based on
113 polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) solution were obtained through the preparation of PVA solution at
114 8% (w/v) in 10% ethanol and curcumin at 7% (w/w) respect to polymer weight. PVA solution
115 was stirred at 90 °C for 2 h and curcumin was added under ethanol when PVA was dissolved.

116

117 *2.2.2. Electrospinning process*

118 Electrospinning was performed using an electrospinning equipment Spraybase®power
119 SupplyUnit (Maynooth, Ireland) with a vertical standard configuration equipped with two

120 pumps, a high voltage power and a collector plate connected to the grounded counter
121 electrode of the power supply. A coaxial device containing two concentric stainless-steel
122 needles (0.7 mm and 2.1 mm of inner diameters) was used to obtain electrospun fibers with
123 core-shell structure. Hydrophilic PVA polymer and hydrophobic PLA were designed in the
124 core and in the shell, respectively. Two core shell structures containing curcumin were
125 designed: i) PLA/PVA-Cur; and ii) PLA.CNC/PVA-Cur, where CNC were added to PLA
126 section to study their effect in the curcumin release kinetic. PVA and PLA polymeric
127 solutions were poured into 5 mL syringes and pumped by using different feed rates:
128 PLA/PVA-Cur: 0.4 and 1.5 mL/h for the core and shell, respectively; and b) PLA.CNC/PVA-
129 Cur: 0.6 and 2.25 mL/h for the core and shell, respectively, because the presence of the CNCs
130 induced the use of higher flow rate. A collector plate covered with aluminum foil was used
131 to collect electrospun fibers with a distance of 14 cm between the tip of the needle and the
132 collector plate. During coaxial electrospinning, the applied voltage ranged between 10 and
133 13 kV. The electrospinning process was executed during 2 h, which resulted in the formation
134 of a membrane of approximately 8 cm in diameter and sufficient thickness to handle (15-20
135 μm , approximately). PLA, PVA, PLA-Cur and PVA-Cur mats were also manufactured by
136 using the single emitter (0.7 mm diameter) electrospinning by using the same solutions
137 described above. Processing parameters were adjusted at a feed rate of 2 and 1 mL/h for PLA
138 and PVA solutions, respectively. Voltage applied varied between 12 and 13 kV and the
139 distance between the tip of the capillary and the collecting plate was maintained at 14 cm.
140 All mats were dried in an oven at 40 °C for 24 h for further analysis. Figure 1 represents
141 schematically the structures of active fibers.

142

143 *2.3. Characterization of electrospun fibers*

144

145 *2.3.1. Morphological analysis*

146 The morphology of the active electrospun mats PLA/PVA-Cur, PLA.CNC/PVA-Cur and
147 PLA-Cur were studied using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) JSM-5410 Jeol with
148 accelerating voltage at 10 kV. Samples were coated with gold palladium using a Sputtering
149 System Hummer 6.2, and SEM micrographs of the surface were taken. Average fiber
150 diameters were analysed with image analyser software (Image J v1.37).

151

152 *2.3.2. Structural analysis*

153 Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy was used to characterize the presence of
154 specific chemical groups from active mats and possible chemical interactions between their
155 components. FTIR spectra were performed in Attenuated Total Reflection (ATR) mode with
156 a Bruker IFS 66V spectrometer. The spectra were the results of 64 coadded interferograms
157 at 4 cm^{-1} and resolutions in the wavenumber range from 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} . The spectra
158 analyses were performed using OPUS Software Version 7.

159 Structures of active electrospun mats and their corresponding components were also
160 evaluated through X-ray diffraction (XRD). XRD patterns were measured using a Siemens
161 Diffractometer D5000 (30 mA and 40 kV) using CuK α ($\lambda = 1.54\text{\AA}$) radiation at room
162 temperature. All scans were performed in a 2θ range $2\text{--}12^\circ$ at $0.02^\circ/\text{s}$.

163

164 *2.3.3. Thermal properties*

165 Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) analyses of electrospun mats were carry out with
166 a Mettler-Toledo model STAR 822e (Schwerzenbach, Switzerland) coupled to a cooling unit
167 (HAAKE EK 90/mt, Newington, USA). 6-8 mg of each sample were subjected to a thermal

168 heating scan from 0 to 250 °C, at a constant speed of 10 °C /min under nitrogen atmosphere.
169 The parameters reported were the glass transition temperature (T_g), melting temperature (T_m),
170 cold crystallization temperature (T_{cc}), melting (ΔH_m) and cold crystallization enthalpies
171 (ΔH_{cc}). The crystallinity was calculated following Eq. 1:

$$172 \quad X_c = \% \text{ crystallinity of PLA} = 100 \times [(\Delta H_m - \Delta H_{cc}) / \Delta H_m^0] \quad (1)$$

173 where ΔH_m is the specific melting enthalpy of the sample ($J g^{-1}$); ΔH_{cc} is the specific cold
174 crystallization enthalpy of the sample ($J g^{-1}$) and ΔH_m^0 is the specific melting enthalpy of a
175 wholly crystalline PLA ($93.6 J g^{-1}$) (Ambrosio-Martín, Fabra, Lopez-Rubio, & Lagaron,
176 2015).

177 Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of single and coaxial mats were performed using a
178 Mettler Toledo Gas Controller GC20 Stare System TGA/DCS (Schwerzenbach,
179 Switzerland). Approximately 7 mg of each sample were deposited in porcelain capsules,
180 which were subjected to a temperature scan from 30 to 600 °C at 10 °C min^{-1} heating rate of
181 10 °C min^{-1} under nitrogen atmosphere (flow rate 50 mL min^{-1}).

182

183 *2.4 Study of the release kinetics of curcumin from active electrospun fibers*

184

185 *2.4.1 Release assay procedure*

186 The release kinetics of an active compound from a packaging polymer matrix to a food is
187 the result of the combination between mass transfer phenomena that involves equilibrium
188 and kinetic processes in both food, headspace and packaging material (Chen, Chen, Xu, &
189 Yam, 2019). The equilibrium is expressed in terms of the partition coefficient of the active
190 compound, thermodynamic parameter that corresponds to the ratio between the concentration
191 of the active compound in the polymer and in the food simulant ($K_{P/FS} = C_P / C_{FS}$). Meanwhile,

192 the kinetic process is defined in terms of the diffusion coefficient (D_p) of the active compound
193 inside the polymeric matrix and corresponds to the kinetic parameter that measures the
194 particle speed diffusion in a polymer matrix to reach the thermodynamic equilibrium
195 (Galotto, Torres, Guarda, Moraga, & Romero, 2011; Torres, Guarda, Moraga, Romero, &
196 Galotto, 2012). Thus, the diffusion coefficient of the active compound inside the polymeric
197 matrix and the partition coefficient between the polymer matrix and the food phase
198 correspond to the key parameters in the design of an active packaging.

199 Curcumin release kinetics were characterized by means of specific experimental migration
200 assays using 10 and 50% ethanol solutions as food simulants in order to describe the mass
201 transfer of curcumin from uniaxial PLA and core-shell electrospun PLA/PVA mats.
202 Migration studies were conducted in accordance with the European Committee for
203 Standardization according to EU Regulations (UNE-EN 1186-3) according to the
204 methodology detailed in previous work (Galotto et al., 2011; Rojas et al., 2015; Torres,
205 Romero, Macan, Guarda, & Galotto, 2014). Electrospun mats loaded with curcumin were
206 totally immersed into glass tubes filled with the food simulants. Samples were placed in the
207 migration tubes using metal supports in order to avoid direct contact between samples and
208 with the tube's wall. Release tubes were placed at 40 °C and periodically analyzed during at
209 least 2 days. Food simulant samples of 1 mL were collected from the migration tubes as a
210 function of time without replacement since its replacement would generate a curcumin
211 quantification error higher than its value without refill. Released curcumin was periodically
212 analyzed through UV spectroscopy at 425 nm using a UV-VIS Spectrophotometer Pharo 300
213 Spectroquant® (Germany). The calibration curve was made by fitting peak area and
214 curcumin concentration of standard solutions from 0.001 to 0.005 g/L, with three samples
215 for each curcumin concentration. Release assays were carried out until the equilibrium

216 condition was observed, when concentration of curcumin becomes practically constant in
217 time in at least two continuous consecutive measurements.

218

219 *2.4.2 Determination of partition and diffusion coefficients of curcumin in PLA/PVA coaxial-* 220 *electrospun mats*

221 Figure 2 shows an outline of the system analyzed in this work. Figure 2a shows curcumin
222 transfer through coaxial electrospun PLA/PVA-Cur mat. In these mats, the mass transfer was
223 driven by the concentration gradient of curcumin with discontinuous profile at the interface
224 where the thermodynamic equilibrium between the polymer and liquid food simulant phase
225 was established. Meanwhile, Figure 2b shows curcumin transfer through PLA.CNC/PVA
226 electrospun mat, which are represented as a non-continuous system because CNC inclusion
227 in PLA matrix. These systems were described by means of an effective Fick's law approach
228 where the PLA.CNC ensemble is considered a continuous medium in terms of its
229 mathematical description. Thus, the mass transfer process for the analyzed systems can be
230 explained by means of a resistances-in-series approach based on the one-dimensional
231 simplification of Fick's Law (Crank, 1975; Galotto et al., 2011; Torres et al., 2012).

232 Therefore, instantaneous mass transfer of curcumin can be estimated by molecular
233 diffusion through the materials. This mechanism can be described through Eq. 2:

$$234 \quad J_I = \frac{D_{eff}}{L/2} \cdot C_{Cur}^P(x = 0, t) - C_{Cur}^P(x = L/2, t) \quad (2)$$

235 Where J_I is the mass transfer flux ($\text{kg m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) of the released curcumin through the electrospun
236 mat, D_{eff} is the effective diffusion coefficient of curcumin in the materials ($\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$), C_{Cur}^P (kg
237 m^{-3}) is the concentration of curcumin in the material bulk, and L is the film thickness (m). In
238 this case, the configuration of the release experiments allows the symmetrical description of

239 the mass transfer with Eq. 2 from both sides of the electrospun mat. The dimensionless
240 distribution coefficient of curcumin between the electrospun mats and the food simulant is
241 represented by the ratio of concentrations in the interface, as Eq. 3 describes:

$$242 \quad K_{P/FS} = \frac{C_{Cur}^P(x=L/2,t)}{C_{Cur}^{FS}(x=L/2,t)} \quad (3)$$

243 This coefficient can be directly estimated from the results of the release experiments at
244 the equilibrium condition, where $C_{Cur}^{FS}(x=L/2,t)$ is the equilibrium concentration of
245 curcumin at the interface in the food simulant and $C_{Cur}^P(x=L/2,t)$ is its value at the
246 interface in the electrospun mat. This last value can be estimated as a function of time through
247 mass balance.

248 Finally, the next step in the release process is the transfer through the boundary layer in
249 the food simulant phase at the proximities of the interface. The transfer mechanism
250 considered in the model was natural convection because the food simulant solutions were not
251 stirred during the release assays. Thus, this step can be described by Eq. 4:

$$252 \quad J_{II} = k \cdot (C_{Cur}^{FS}(x=L/2,t) - C_{Cur}^{FS}(x=\infty,t)) \quad (4)$$

253 Where C_{Cur}^{FS} is the curcumin concentration in the food simulant bulk (kg m^{-3}) and k (m s^{-1}) is
254 the curcumin mass transfer coefficient that quantifies natural convection in the food liquid
255 phase and its value was calculated by means of the correlation reported by Galotto and
256 coworkers, where the coefficient is obtained from the Sherwood number, which is calculated
257 as a function of the Grashof and Schmidt numbers (Galotto et al., 2011). A few assumptions
258 had to be made in order to use this model:

259 1. - The initial curcumin concentration in the materials is known and is homogeneously
260 distributed, $C_{Cur}^P(x=0,t) = C_{Cur,0}^P = 0 \leq x \leq L/2$

261 2. - The food simulant is initially curcumin-free: $C_{Cur}^{FS}(x,0) = 0$

- 262 3. - There is no chemical interaction between food simulant and polymer (no swelling).
263 4. - There is no mass transfer limitation in the liquid food simulant, so curcumin is always
264 homogeneously distributed in the food simulant.

265 These mathematical model equations describing molecular diffusion of curcumin through
266 the materials, as well as the polymer/food simulant distribution coefficient and transfer
267 through the boundary layer in the food simulant phase at the proximities of the material/food
268 interface were applied in a previous study developed by the same working group (Galotto et
269 al., 2011; Rojas et al., 2015; Torres, Romero, et al., 2014). Mass transfer equations were
270 solved under steady-state condition for an instantaneous time. Regula Falsi method was
271 applied in order to reduce the number of interfacial concentration values of curcumin
272 iterations. Taking into account that the initial curcumin concentration in the electrospun mats
273 and the simulant bulk are known, an iterative calculation can be done to estimate the mass
274 transfer flux through the interface at steady-state condition ($J_I = J_{II}$) for a specific time step.
275 Iterative variables in this calculation are the interfacial concentrations of curcumin in both
276 phases. When this numerical solution was identified, the bulk concentrations of curcumin in
277 the polymer and in the food simulant were recalculated by mass balance, starting a new
278 iterative calculation for the next time step. These calculations were implemented by means
279 of a program built in Matlab 7.1. Simulations were developed, using experimental values of
280 the $K_{P/FS}$ defined in equation 3. Different De_{eff} values of curcumin in the materials were
281 considered involving the lowest values of RMSE (root of the mean-square error) between
282 experimental data and values predicted by the mathematical model. The root of the mean-
283 square error (RMSE (%)) was calculated using Eq. 5. This measures the fit between
284 experimental and estimated data:

285
$$RMSE = \frac{1}{M_{M,0}} \cdot \sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{N}\right) \cdot \sum_{i=1}^N \left((M_{FS,t})_{experimental,i} - (M_{FS,t})_{predicted,i} \right)^2}$$

286 (5)

286 Where N is the number of experimental points for each release curve; i is the observations
 287 number; $M_{M,0}$ is the initial amount of curcumin in the material (μg) and $M_{FS,t}$ is the curcumin
 288 amount in the food simulatant at time t (μg).

289

290 *2.5. Statistical analysis*

291

292 A randomized experimental design was considered for the experiments. Data analysis was
 293 carried out using Statgraphics Plus 5.1. This software was used to implement variance
 294 analysis and Fisher's LSD test. Differences were considered significant at $P < 0.05$.

295

296 **3. Results and discussion**

297

298 *3.1. Morphological characterization*

299

300 SEM microscopies and the average diameter of the electrospun fibrillary mats are depicted
 301 in Figure 3. PLA-Cur fibers did not evidence beads and presented an average diameter of 682
 302 ± 192 nm. Meanwhile, PLA/PVA-Cur and PLA.CNC/PVA-Cur solutions rendered
 303 continuous flattened ribbon-like fibers with an average diameter of (2822 ± 732) nm and
 304 (2834 ± 310) nm, respectively.

305 The flattened ribbon-like morphology of the coaxial fiber could be the result of fiber
 306 collapse due to the atmospheric pressure induced by higher evaporation of the solvent in the

307 shell solution (chloroform) than of the core solution (water) (Pant, Park, & Park, 2019).
308 Meanwhile, the higher average diameter of the coaxial samples were probably related to the
309 fact that flow rates used for these developments were 1.5 times higher than uniaxial flow rate
310 process (Qin, 2017).

311

312 *3.2. Attenuated total reflectance Fourier transform infrared (ATR-FTIR) spectroscopy*

313

314 FTIR spectroscopy was performed to identify specific interactions between curcumin and
315 the chemical polymeric groups and therefore, understanding the release process of curcumin
316 from coaxial electrospun fibers. Particularly, the thermodynamic equilibrium in the release
317 process will depend closely on molecular interactions between curcumin and the polymer
318 matrix. Figure 4 shows the FTIR spectra of PLA, curcumin and electrospun composites
319 containing curcumin.

320 FTIR spectra of PLA-Cur presented similar pattern with PLA, evidencing any
321 characteristic absorption bands of curcumin. Characteristic peaks of PLA were found
322 between: i) 1350 and 1450 cm^{-1} (-C-H-); ii) 1039-2366 cm^{-1} (-C-O- stretching); and iii) 860
323 cm^{-1} (C-C-). The lack of peaks assigned to the curcumin structure between 1628 and 539 cm^{-1}
324 ¹ could be due to the overlapping with peaks associated to PLA structure, whose intensity
325 were greatly higher due to the low concentration of curcumin. Moreover, the characteristic
326 peak of curcumin near 3507 cm^{-1} assigned to its hydroxyls groups was not evidenced in PLA-
327 Cur spectra. The absence of this band could be due to the interaction between curcumin and
328 PLA through intermolecular hydrogen bonding (Mamidi, Romo, Barrera, Elías-Zúñiga, &
329 Elías-Zúñiga, 2018). This interaction was also evidenced by the displacement of the carbonyl
330 (C=O) stretching band from 1744 cm^{-1} for neat PLA to 1751 cm^{-1} for PLA-Cur mat. Other

331 works regarding electrospun PLA fibers containing active compounds have evidenced
332 displacements of PLA characteristic peaks (Altan, Aytac, & Uyar, 2018).

333 FTIR spectra of coaxial mats presented mostly characteristic PLA spectra pattern. This
334 fact occurred because this technique is able to identify functional groups from first layer of
335 materials. Thus, PLA was the mainly polymer detected, while PVA and curcumin bands from
336 core structure were not evidenced thanks to the successful encapsulation of PVA containing
337 curcumin nanofiber, whose amount represented only 17% (w/w respect total mat weight)
338 over the coaxial fiber. Although PVA characteristic peaks and their corresponding
339 displacements were not detected, chemical interactions through hydrogen bonding between
340 PVA and curcumin in the core section of active electrospun coaxial mats could occur. PVA
341 hydroxyl groups could act as hydrogen bond donors or acceptors leading to potential
342 hydrogen bond interactions with both curcumin hydrogen bond donors and acceptor moieties
343 (Buslov, Sushko, & Tretinnikov, 2011).

344

345 *3.3. X-ray analysis*

346

347 XRD diffractograms of the electrospun coaxial mats are presented in Figure 5. Their
348 components were also analyzed in order to study the effect of their blends on their
349 crystallinities during the electrospinning process. PLA and PVA powders diffraction patterns
350 revealed the intrinsic semicrystalline nature of both polymers. PLA presented a principal
351 characteristic band at 16.8° , and XRD diffractogram of PVA powder indicated two
352 characteristic peaks at $2\Theta = 19.6$ and 40.5° (Kuila & Ray, 2014; López de Dicastillo et al.,
353 2017). Nevertheless, crystallinity of both polymers were diminished after electrospinning
354 process. DRX pattern of electrospun PLA-Cur mat evidenced the characteristic PLA band

355 was broaden and this crystallinity reduction was aggravated through coaxial process in the
356 case of PLA/PVA-Cur mat. Few studies have analyzed the effect of core/shell structures on
357 reduction of crystallinity degree in polymers, but XRD analysis clearly revealed amorphous
358 structures of electrospun mats. These results were in accordance with thermal properties
359 measured through DSC analysis that showed reduction of PLA and PVA crystallinity by
360 incorporation of curcumin and coaxial electrospinning process. On the other hand, although
361 XRD pattern shows a high degree of amorphous nature, the incorporation of CNC into PLA
362 shell structure entailed the definition of the characteristic PLA crystallographic peak,
363 demonstrating its nucleating effect. This fact was already observed on other PLA composites
364 (López de Dicastillo et al., 2017).

365

366 *3.4. Thermal characterization*

367

368 Thermal parameters and the crystallinity of the coaxial and single mats during the heating
369 process are shown in Table 1. The parameters of coaxial mats were studied considering
370 interactions occurring separately in the core and shell. PLA/PVA-Cur mat presented a single
371 melting transition at 145.8 °C, similar to the characteristic melting temperature of PLA,
372 because this polymer was the major component of the fibers (81.4 wt%) (Table 1). PLA
373 crystallinity ($X_{c,PLA}$) of coaxial structure PLA/PVA-Cur was lower than single neat PLA fiber
374 attributed to interfacial interactions between PLA polymeric chains (shell) and PVA-Cur
375 (core) that inhibited chain mobility. This chain mobility reduction caused amorphous zones
376 reordered during heating at 77.5 °C and a higher T_g in PLA/PVA-Cur respect to single PVA-
377 Cur (see Table 1).

378

379 Meanwhile, PLA.CNC/PVA-Cur thermogram revealed melting process of two types of
380 crystals, a melting process at 145.4 °C possibly associated to PLA from shell section
381 PLA.CNC and a second melting process at 180.7 °C attributed to PVA crystals from core
382 section PVA-Cur (Table 1). The presence of CNC could promote hydrogen bonding type
383 interactions in PLA.CNC shell and therefore preferable interactions between PVA and Cur
384 located in the core. This effect could be favored with coaxial electrospinning rates sufficient
385 to prevent mixing of the PVA-Cur and PLA.CNC solutions circulating through the core and
386 shell, respectively (Nguyen, Chung, & Park, 2011). Crystallinity values of PLA and PVA
387 phases in the coaxial fiber PLA.CNC/PVA-Cur were lower than crystallinity of single PLA
388 and PVA fibers (Table 1). This fact was also due to a chain mobility reduction by a higher
389 number of hydrogen bonding type interactions between components in the coaxial fiber:
390 PLA-CNC, PVA-Cur and interfacial interactions core-shell. This mobility restriction caused
391 an increase of T_g values for both coaxial mats and PLA-Cur.

392 On the other hand, neat polymers (PLA and PVA) and single fibers containing Cur were
393 analyzed for a better understanding of the effect of electrospinning process and the
394 incorporation of Cur on thermal properties. Electrospun PLA mat presented glass transition
395 temperature at 40 °C and two melting shoulder peaks at 136.9 and 147.3 °C derived from
396 crystalline structures with different ordering degrees (Gonçalves, da Silva, Picciani, & Dias,
397 2015). The incorporation of Cur shifted PLA glass transition and melting temperatures to
398 higher values due to polymer-Cur interactions. This trend was already observed between
399 curcumin and gelatin (Mamidi et al., 2018). Cur interacted with PLA polymeric chains
400 through hydrogen bonding interaction, decreasing mobility and crystallinity. This effect was
401 in accordance with the results reported for polydioxanone/Cur filaments (Mouthuy et al.,
402 2017). Furthermore, PLA-Cur amorphous region partially cold crystallized during the first

403 heating causing a reordered structure with a unique melting transition (see T_{cc} and T_m in
404 Table 1).

405 First heating process also evidenced electrospinning originated two crystals with different
406 order degrees on PVA and PVA-Cur fibers. The crystalline regions of the PVA involved
407 different types of hydrogen bonds which corresponded to free hydroxyl groups or
408 intermolecular and intramolecular interactions (Masuda, Kaji, & Horii, 2001). The
409 incorporation of Cur significantly increased the crystallinity of the single PVA-Cur fibers. In
410 this case, Cur acted as a nucleating agent causing slight differences in glass and melting
411 temperatures.

412 Thermogravimetric analysis indicated that, although Cur presented early degradation, this
413 compound presented an antioxidant behavior since thermal stabilities of PVA-Cur and PLA-
414 Cur mats were higher than PVA and PLA mats, respectively (Table 2 and Fig. 64). Hydrogen
415 bonds interactions between carbonyl and hydroxyl groups of Cur with the chains of both
416 polymers resulted on more thermal stable structures. This effect was more significant for the
417 PLA-Cur mat, which T_{onset} and $T_{d,max}$ values were greatly increased (Table 2), probably
418 because PLA presents a greater proportion of groups available to form hydrogen-bonding
419 interactions. These interactions were arranged in such a way that the ending hydroxyl groups
420 of the Cur interacted with polymeric chains, reducing their mobility and resulting on a more
421 stable structure, in accordance with the results observed through DSC analysis.

422 On the other hand, coaxial fibers with PVA core containing Cur were more thermal stable
423 than single PVA-Cur fiber (Table 2 and Figure 6). The PLA shell caused a delay in the
424 decomposition and degradation of the PLA/PVA-Cur fiber, considering PLA could interact
425 with PVA and Cur in the interphase core-shell during electrospinning and form a more stable
426 coaxial structure. Nonetheless, the thermal stability of the coaxial fiber was insignificantly

427 varied with the incorporation of CNC into the shell, although nanocrystals degraded at a
428 lower temperature than polymers. This fact was attributed to the low concentration of
429 nanocrystals and the interactions between cellulose and PLA in the shell, in accordance with
430 results shown through DSC measurements.

431

432

433 *3.5. Study of the release kinetics of curcumin from PLA/PVA coaxial-electrospun mats*

434

435 The release kinetics of an active compound from a polymer matrix to a food is the result
436 of the combination of mass transfer phenomena that involves equilibrium and kinetic
437 processes in both food and packaging material. Figure 7 shows the curcumin release kinetics,
438 expressed as mg of curcumin per surface, from developed electrospun mats to food simulants
439 10 and 50% ethanol (v/v). The graphs represent experimental data and theoretical estimations
440 which were obtained through the mass transfer model with correlated diffusion coefficients
441 of curcumin in the electrospun mats.

442 The equilibrium was expressed in terms of the partition coefficient ($K_{P/FS}$) of curcumin
443 (Cur), thermodynamic parameter that corresponded to the ratio between the concentration of
444 Cur in the polymer, C_P , and the concentration of Cur in the food simulant, C_{FS} ($K_{P/FS}=C_P/C_{FS}$).
445 Meanwhile, the kinetic process was defined in terms of the diffusion coefficient (D_p) of Cur
446 inside the polymeric matrix and corresponds to the kinetic parameter that measures the
447 particle speed diffusion in a polymer matrix to reach the thermodynamic equilibrium (Galotto
448 et al., 2011; Torres et al., 2012). Diffusion coefficient of the active compound inside the
449 polymeric matrix as well as its partition coefficient between the polymer matrix and the food
450 phase correspond to the key parameters in the design of an active packaging. In this study,

451 Cur release kinetics was characterized by means of specific experimental assays using 10 and
452 50% (v/v) ethanolic solutions, as food simulants, in order to describe the mass transfer of
453 curcumin from uniaxial PLA and PLA/PVA coaxial electrospun mats. Thus, partition
454 coefficient of curcumin at the interphase between the material and food simulants and its
455 diffusion coefficient in the electrospun samples were calculated. The partition coefficient
456 was estimated when the released curcumin reached the plateau during each release kinetics
457 profile. Table 3 shows partition ($K_{P/F}$) and diffusion coefficient (D_p) values of curcumin from
458 electrospun mats and values of root mean square error (RMSE) of the model solution related
459 to experimental data.

460 Coaxial mats containing curcumin presented considerably higher $K_{P/SA}$ values than PLA-
461 Cur mats, and this tendency was observed for both food simulants. The lowest $K_{P/SA}$ values
462 were found into 50% (v/v) ethanol due to the high affinity between Cur and ethanol. Since
463 all the electrospun mats presented the same initial amount of curcumin, $K_{P/SA}$ differences
464 were consequence of different affinities between curcumin and the polymer matrices. The
465 presence of curcumin into a thin inner PVA fiber increased the affinity between curcumin
466 and this polymer phase. This fact could be explained because PVA is a polymer that contains
467 both donor and acceptor hydrogen, allowing the appearance of hydrogen bonds with both
468 curcumin donors and acceptor moieties, and PLA only contains hydrogen. Particularly, some
469 studies have reported that practically every hydroxyl groups from PVA interact with other
470 hydroxyl groups and act as both a proton donor and acceptor (Buslov et al., 2011). Thus, the
471 cohesive energy between curcumin and PVA polymer matrix was high, decreasing the
472 amount of curcumin released into the food simulants.

473 Figure 7 also indicates curcumin released at the equilibrium time for PLA/PVA-Cur and
474 PLA.CNC/PVA-Cur mats were not significantly different. $K_{P/SA}$ values of both materials

475 were very similar (Table 3). This fact is interesting because it indicated that, although the
476 addition of CNC in PLA outer matrix delayed curcumin release, the presence of these
477 nanostructures did not play any role in the cohesive energy established between curcumin
478 and the polymer matrix. As shown by release kinetic curves in Fig. 7 and RMSE values in
479 Table 3, theoretical curves greatly fitted with the experimental data. Curcumin released from
480 uniaxial PLA and coaxial PLA/PVA mats were mainly controlled by the diffusion
481 phenomenon in the polymer defined by the second Fick's law. This behavior was in
482 agreement with the release of other active agents from electrospun fibers (Estevez-Areco,
483 Guz, Candal, & Goyanes, 2018; López de Dicastillo et al., 2018; Xu, Chen, Ma, Wang, &
484 Jing, 2008). The curve slope of the kinetic of released curcumin greatly depended on the mat
485 structure (uniaxial or coaxial mats), the presence of CNC in the shell-PLA polymer matrix,
486 and on the type of food simulant. **Table 3** also presents the values of diffusion coefficient of
487 curcumin through uniaxial mat PLA-Cur and coaxial PLA/PVA-Cur and PLA.CNC/PVA-
488 Cur mats in 10% and 50% ethanol. Coefficient diffusion of curcumin in PLA-Cur presented
489 different values as function of the food simulant used. The diffusion coefficient of curcumin
490 estimated for release test using 10% ethanol was $5.0 \times 10^{-13} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$. Any previous data on
491 curcumin diffusion coefficient of electrospun samples has been reported, but as reference
492 point, this value was lower than diffusion coefficient of cinnamaldehyde ($1.0 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$)
493 in PLA electrospun fibers (López de Dicastillo et al., 2018). This result was expected because
494 diffusion coefficient magnitude decreased as molecular weight of the solute increased. On
495 the other hand, diffusion coefficient value of curcumin in the uniaxial sample using 50%
496 (v/v) ethanol presented a 16-fold increase ($5.5 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) due to the high affinity between
497 PLA and ethanol. The PLA plasticization and swelling due to the penetration of the food
498 simulant to the polymer matrix modified the effective transport properties of PLA during the

499 release assay improving curcumin mass transfer and overestimating the value of the diffusion
500 coefficient of curcumin in the polymer matrix. Diffusion coefficients reported in Table 3 also
501 exhibited that the coaxial structure of (PLA/PVA-Cur) mats slightly decreased the diffusion
502 coefficient of curcumin with respect to the values obtained in the uniaxial mode (PLA-Cur).
503 PLA/PVA-Cur mat displayed curcumin diffusion coefficient values between 5.0 and 5.5 x
504 $10^{-13} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ without significant differences between food simulants, demonstrating no
505 evidences of swelling during release assays in 50% ethanol v/v as it was observed for the
506 uniaxial sample. The decrease in the diffusion coefficient observed in the coaxial material
507 could be related to the fact that curcumin is distributed in a thin inner PVA layer. Thus,
508 curcumin must diffuse through the entire PLA shell-layer before being released in the food
509 simulant. In the case of the uniaxial PLA-Cur sample, curcumin diffusion occurred only from
510 the porous surface. Moreover, PLA layer in the coaxial mat PLA/PVA-Cur sample presented
511 higher crystallinity degree than in the uniaxial mat PLA-Cur sample that could hinder the
512 diffusion of curcumin in this material. The addition of CNC into the PLA shell layer of the
513 coaxial mat slowed down the diffusion of curcumin, showing a value of diffusion coefficient
514 six times lower ($6.0 \times 10^{-14} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) than CNC-free coaxial sample. This decrease could be
515 explained mainly in terms of the generation of a tortuous path generated by the presence of
516 the CNC during curcumin release, as it was corroborated by XRD assays.

517

518 **4. Conclusions**

519 The present investigation was carried out with the aim to evaluate the feasibility of using
520 electrospinning process coupled with nanotechnology to generate core-shell electrospun
521 composites with a sustained release of curcumin. In a first step, core-shell electrospun mats

522 loaded with 1.23% (w/w) of curcumin (PLA/PVA-Cur and PVA.CNC/PVA-Cur) were
523 developed by means of coaxial electrospinning. Meanwhile, a PLA uniaxial mat was used as
524 reference release material. All active electrospun samples were characterized by their
525 morphological (SEM), structural (FTIR-ATR and XRD) and thermal (DSC and TGA)
526 properties in order to correlate physical properties such as morphology and crystallinity with
527 curcumin release kinetics. The experimental distribution coefficients ($K_{P/SA}$) values of
528 curcumin for the core-shell electrospun PLA/PVA mats were higher than the obtained for the
529 uniaxial PLA because PVA is able to interact with curcumin in a more efficient way than
530 PLA, increasing the cohesive energy between curcumin and the polymer. Meanwhile, no
531 differences in the $K_{P/SA}$ values were obtained due to the presence of CNC in the shell PLA of
532 coaxial fibers.

533 The experimental $K_{P/SA}$ values and some structural properties of the electrospun samples
534 were employed in a phenomenological mass transfer model based on a resistance-in-series
535 approach to correlate the effective diffusion coefficient of curcumin in the electrospun
536 samples during the release studies. The effective coefficient diffusion for coaxial PLA/PVA
537 samples were slightly lower than the value for the uniaxial PLA sample. Furthermore, this
538 value decreased notoriously with the incorporation of CNC in the PLA shell matrix,
539 indicating that the CNC creates a tortuous path inside PLA layer that could make more
540 difficult the diffusion of curcumin through the PLA matrix. In this work, the modification of
541 the transport properties of a core-shell fiber by modifying the $K_{P/SA}$, as function of polymeric
542 structures in order to generate different cohesive energies between the active compound and
543 the core-shell fiber, or modifying the D_{eff} (kinetics) using a nanofiller was achieved. These
544 results show the potential use of coaxial electrospinning process coupled to nanotechnology

545 to generate sustainable active polymer with tunable release properties to be used in food
546 packaging.

547

548 **Acknowledgements**

549 The authors acknowledge the financial support of CONICYT through the Project
550 Fondecyt Regular 1170624, CONICYT Fondecyt Postdoctoral Grant 3190929 and
551 “Programa de Financiamiento Basal para Centros Científicos y Tecnológicos de Excelencia”
552 Project FB0807.

553

554

555 **REFERENCES**

556

557 Alazab, M., Mitchell, G. R., Davis, F. J., & Mohan, S. D. (2017). Sustainable Electrospinning of
558 Nanoscale Fibres. *Procedia Manufacturing*, *12*, 66–78.

559 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.PROMFG.2017.08.009>

560 Altan, A., Aytac, Z., & Uyar, T. (2018). Carvacrol loaded electrospun fibrous films from zein and
561 poly(lactic acid) for active food packaging. *Food Hydrocolloids*, *81*, 48–59.

562 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODHYD.2018.02.028>

563 Alvarado, N., Romero, J., Torres, A., López de Dicastillo, C., Rojas, A., Galotto, M. J., & Guarda,
564 A. (2018). Supercritical impregnation of thymol in poly(lactic acid) filled with electrospun

565 poly(vinyl alcohol)-cellulose nanocrystals nanofibers: Development an active food packaging
566 material. *Journal of Food Engineering*, *217*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2017.08.008>

567 Alvarado, Nancy, Romero, J., Torres, A., López de Dicastillo, C., Rojas, A., Galotto, M. J., &

568 Guarda, A. (2018). Supercritical impregnation of thymol in poly(lactic acid) filled with

569 electrospun poly(vinyl alcohol)-cellulose nanocrystals nanofibers: Development an active food

570 packaging material. *Journal of Food Engineering*, 217, 1–10.
571 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JFOODENG.2017.08.008>

572 Ambrosio-Martín, J., Fabra, M. J., Lopez-Rubio, A., & Lagaron, J. M. (2015). Melt
573 polycondensation to improve the dispersion of bacterial cellulose into polylactide via melt
574 compounding: enhanced barrier and mechanical properties. *Cellulose*, 22(2), 1201–1226.
575 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10570-014-0523-9>

576 Aytac, Z., & Uyar, T. (2017). Core-shell nanofibers of curcumin/cyclodextrin inclusion complex
577 and polylactic acid: Enhanced water solubility and slow release of curcumin. *International*
578 *Journal of Pharmaceutics*, 518(1–2), 177–184. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2016.12.061>

579 Buslov, D. K., Sushko, N. I., & Tretinnikov, O. N. (2011). IR investigation of hydrogen bonds in
580 weakly hydrated films of poly(vinyl alcohol). *Polymer Science Series A*, 53(12), 1121–1127.
581 <https://doi.org/10.1134/S0965545X11120030>

582 Casasola, R., Thomas, N. L., Trybala, A., & Georgiadou, S. (2014). Electrospun poly lactic acid
583 (PLA) fibres: Effect of different solvent systems on fibre morphology and diameter. *Polymer*,
584 55(18), 4728–4737. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.POLYMER.2014.06.032>

585 Chen, X., Chen, M., Xu, C., & Yam, K. L. (2019). Critical review of controlled release packaging
586 to improve food safety and quality. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, 59(15),
587 2386–2399. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2018.1453778>

588 Chen, X., Lee, D. S., Zhu, X., & Yam, K. L. (2012). Release Kinetics of Tocopherol and Quercetin
589 from Binary Antioxidant Controlled-Release Packaging Films. *Journal of Agricultural and*
590 *Food Chemistry*, 60(13), 3492–3497. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf2045813>

591 Crank, J. (1975). *The mathematics of diffusion*. Clarendon Press.

592 Estevez-Areco, S., Guz, L., Candal, R., & Goyanes, S. (2018). Release kinetics of rosemary
593 (Rosmarinus officinalis) polyphenols from polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) electrospun nanofibers in
594 several food simulants. *Food Packaging and Shelf Life*, 18, 42–50.
595 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FPSL.2018.08.006>

596 Ezhilarasi, P. N., Karthik, P., Chhanwal, N., & Anandharamakrishnan, C. (2013).
597 Nanoencapsulation Techniques for Food Bioactive Components: A Review. *Food and*
598 *Bioprocess Technology*, 6(3), 628–647. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11947-012-0944-0>

599 Fortunati, E., Peltzer, M., Armentano, I., Jiménez, A., & Kenny, J. M. (2013). Combined effects of
600 cellulose nanocrystals and silver nanoparticles on the barrier and migration properties of PLA
601 nano-biocomposites. *Journal of Food Engineering*, 118(1), 117–124.
602 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfoodeng.2013.03.025>

603 Galotto, M. J., Torres, A., Guarda, A., Moraga, N., & Romero, J. (2011). Experimental and
604 theoretical study of LDPE versus different concentrations of Irganox 1076 and different
605 thickness. *Food Research International*, 44(2), 566–574.
606 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODRES.2010.12.009>

607 Gómez-Estaca, J., López-de-Dicastillo, C., Hernández-Muñoz, P., Catalá, R., & Gavara, R. (2014).
608 Advances in antioxidant active food packaging. *Trends in Food Science and Technology*,
609 35(1). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2013.10.008>

610 Gonçalves, R. P., da Silva, F. F. F., Picciani, P. H. S., & Dias, M. L. (2015). Morphology and
611 Thermal Properties of Core-Shell PVA/PLA Ultrafine Fibers Produced by Coaxial
612 Electrospinning. *Materials Sciences and Applications*, 06(02), 189–199.
613 <https://doi.org/10.4236/msa.2015.62022>

614 Gong, W., Wei, S., Ruan, S., & Shen, C. (2019). Electrospun coaxial PPESK/PVDF fibrous
615 membranes with thermal shutdown property used for lithium-ion batteries. *Materials Letters*,
616 244, 126–129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MATLET.2019.02.009>

617 Jacobsen, C., García-Moreno, P. J., Mendes, A. C., Mateiu, R. V., & Chronakis, I. S. (2018). Use of
618 Electrohydrodynamic Processing for Encapsulation of Sensitive Bioactive Compounds and
619 Applications in Food. *Annual Review of Food Science and Technology*, 9(1), 525–549.
620 <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-food-030117-012348>

621 Johnson, R., Ding, Y., Nagiah, N., Monnet, E., & Tan, W. (2019). Coaxially-structured fibres with

622 tailored material properties for vascular graft implant. *Materials Science and Engineering: C*,
623 97, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MSEC.2018.11.036>

624 Koski, A., Yim, K., & Shivkumar, S. (2004). Effect of molecular weight on fibrous PVA produced
625 by electrospinning. *Materials Letters*, 58(3–4), 493–497. <https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167->
626 577X(03)00532-9

627 Kuila, S. B., & Ray, S. K. (2014). Dehydration of dioxane by pervaporation using filled blend
628 membranes of polyvinyl alcohol and sodium alginate. *Carbohydrate Polymers*, 101, 1154–
629 1165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CARBPOL.2013.09.086>

630 López de Dicastillo, C., Bustos, F., Valenzuela, X., López-Carballo, G., Vilariño, J. M., & Galotto,
631 M. J. (2017). Chilean berry *Ugni molinae* Turcz. fruit and leaves extracts with interesting
632 antioxidant, antimicrobial and tyrosinase inhibitory properties. *Food Research International*,
633 102, 119–128. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodres.2017.09.073>

634 López de Dicastillo, C., Garrido, L., Alvarado, N., Romero, J., Palma, J., & Galotto, M. (2017).
635 Improvement of Polylactide Properties through Cellulose Nanocrystals Embedded in
636 Poly(Vinyl Alcohol) Electrospun Nanofibers. *Nanomaterials*, 7(5), 106.
637 <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano7050106>

638 López de Dicastillo, C., Roa, K., Garrido, L., Pereira, A., & Galotto, M. (2017). Novel Polyvinyl
639 Alcohol/Starch Electrospun Fibers as a Strategy to Disperse Cellulose Nanocrystals into
640 Poly(lactic acid). *Polymers*, 9(4), 117. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym9040117>

641 López de Dicastillo, C., Villegas, C., Garrido, L., Roa, K., Torres, A., José Galotto, M., ... Romero,
642 J. (2018). Modifying an Active Compound's Release Kinetic Using a Supercritical
643 Impregnation Process to Incorporate an Active Agent into PLA Electrospun Mats. *Polymers*,
644 10, 479. <https://doi.org/10.3390/polym10050479>

645 Mamidi, N., Romo, I. L., Barrera, E. V., Elías-Zúñiga, A., & Elías-Zúñiga, A. (2018). High
646 throughput fabrication of curcumin embedded gelatin-poly(lactic acid) electrospun fiber-aligned
647 scaffolds for the controlled release of curcumin. *MRS Communications*, 8(04), 1395–1403.

648 <https://doi.org/10.1557/mrc.2018.193>

649 Manepalli, P. H., & Alavi, S. (2019). Mathematical modeling of mechanical and barrier properties
650 of poly(lactic acid)/poly(butylene adipate-co-terephthalate)/thermoplastic starch based
651 nanocomposites. *Journal of Food Engineering*, *261*, 60–65.
652 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JFOODENG.2019.04.004>

653 Martínez-Sanz, M., Lopez-Rubio, A., & Lagaron, J. M. (2013). High-barrier coated bacterial
654 cellulose nanowhiskers films with reduced moisture sensitivity. *Carbohydrate Polymers*,
655 *98*(1), 1072–1082. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CARBPOL.2013.07.020>

656 Masuda, K., Kaji, H., & Horii, F. (2001). Studies on Different Types of Hydrogen Bonds in
657 Poly(vinyl alcohol) Films by 1H CRAMPS and Solid-State Two-Dimensional 1H-13C
658 Heteronuclear Correlation Analyses. *Polymer Journal*, *33*(2), 190–198.
659 <https://doi.org/10.1295/polymj.33.190>

660 Mouthuy, P.-A., Somogyi Škoc, M., Čipak Gašparović, A., Milković, L., Carr, A. J., & Žarković,
661 N. (2017). Investigating the use of curcumin-loaded electrospun filaments for soft tissue repair
662 applications. *International Journal of Nanomedicine*, *Volume 12*, 3977–3991.
663 <https://doi.org/10.2147/IJN.S133326>

664 Nguyen, T. T. T., Chung, O. H., & Park, J. S. (2011). Coaxial electrospun poly(lactic acid)/chitosan
665 (core/shell) composite nanofibers and their antibacterial activity. *Carbohydrate Polymers*,
666 *86*(4), 1799–1806. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2011.07.014>

667 Pant, B., Park, M., & Park, S.-J. (2019). Drug Delivery Applications of Core-Sheath Nanofibers
668 Prepared by Coaxial Electrospinning: A Review. *Pharmaceutics*, *11*(7).
669 <https://doi.org/10.3390/pharmaceutics11070305>

670 Qian, S., Sheng, K., Yu, K., Xu, L., & Fontanillo Lopez, C. A. (2018). Improved properties of PLA
671 biocomposites toughened with bamboo cellulose nanowhiskers through silane modification.
672 *Journal of Materials Science*, *53*(15), 10920–10932. [https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-018-](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-018-2377-2)
673 [2377-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-018-2377-2)

674 Qin, X. (2017). Coaxial electrospinning of nanofibers. In *Electrospun Nanofibers* (pp. 41–71).
675 Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-100907-9.00003-9>

676 Quiles-Carrillo, L., Montanes, N., Lagaron, J., Balart, R., & Torres-Giner, S. (2019). Bioactive
677 Multilayer Polylactide Films with Controlled Release Capacity of Gallic Acid Accomplished
678 by Incorporating Electrospun Nanostructured Coatings and Interlayers. *Applied Sciences*, 9(3),
679 533. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app9030533>

680 Rojas, A., Cerro, D., Torres, A., Galotto, M. J., Guarda, A., & Romero, J. (2015). Supercritical
681 impregnation and kinetic release of 2-nonanone in LLDPE films used for active food
682 packaging. *The Journal of Supercritical Fluids*, 104, 76–84.
683 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.supflu.2015.04.031>

684 Shehata, N., Gaballah, S., Samir, E., Hamed, A., & Saad, M. (2016). Fluorescent Nanocomposite of
685 Embedded Ceria Nanoparticles in Crosslinked PVA Electrospun Nanofibers. *Nanomaterials*
686 (*Basel, Switzerland*), 6(6). <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano6060102>

687 Torres-Martinez, E. J., Cornejo Bravo, J. M., Serrano Medina, A., Pérez González, G. L., &
688 Villarreal Gómez, L. J. (2018). A Summary of Electrospun Nanofibers as Drug Delivery
689 System: Drugs Loaded and Biopolymers Used as Matrices. *Current Drug Delivery*, 15(10),
690 1360–1374. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1567201815666180723114326>

691 Torres, A., Guarda, A., Moraga, N., Romero, J., & Galotto, M. J. (2012). Experimental and
692 theoretical study of thermodynamics and transport properties of multilayer polymeric food
693 packaging. *European Food Research and Technology*, 234(4), 713–722.
694 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00217-012-1683-1>

695 Torres, A., López de Dicastillo, C., Ríos, M., Bastías, I., Guarda, A., & Galotto, M. J. (2014). Effect
696 or organoclay incorporation on thermal, physical and morphological properties of LLDPE
697 nanocomposites for active food packaging applications. *Journal of the Chilean Chemical*
698 *Society*, 59(4), 2681–2685. <https://doi.org/10.4067/S0717-97072014000400011>

699 Torres, A., Romero, J., Macan, A., Guarda, A., & Galotto, M. J. (2014). Near critical and

700 supercritical impregnation and kinetic release of thymol in LLDPE films used for food
701 packaging. *The Journal of Supercritical Fluids*, 85, 41–48.
702 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.supflu.2013.10.011>

703 Tsuji, H. (2013). Poly(Lactic Acid). In *Bio-Based Plastics* (pp. 171–239). Chichester, UK: John
704 Wiley & Sons Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118676646.ch8>

705 Vega-Lugo, A.-C., & Lim, L.-T. (2009). Controlled release of allyl isothiocyanate using soy protein
706 and poly(lactic acid) electrospun fibers. *Food Research International*, 42(8), 933–940.
707 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODRES.2009.05.005>

708 Wang, H., Hao, L., Wang, P., Chen, M., Jiang, S., & Jiang, S. (2017). Release kinetics and
709 antibacterial activity of curcumin loaded zein fibers. *Food Hydrocolloids*, 63, 437–446.
710 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FOODHYD.2016.09.028>

711 Wen, P., Zong, M.-H., Linhardt, R. J., Feng, K., & Wu, H. (2017). Electrospinning: A novel nano-
712 encapsulation approach for bioactive compounds. *Trends in Food Science & Technology*, 70,
713 56–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TIFS.2017.10.009>

714 Xu, X., Chen, X., Ma, P., Wang, X., & Jing, X. (2008). The release behavior of doxorubicin
715 hydrochloride from medicated fibers prepared by emulsion-electrospinning. *European Journal*
716 *of Pharmaceutics and Biopharmaceutics*, 70(1), 165–170.
717 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.EJPB.2008.03.010>

718 Yam, K. L., & Zhu, X. (2012). Controlled release food and beverage packaging. *Emerging Food*
719 *Packaging Technologies*, 13–26. <https://doi.org/10.1533/9780857095664.1.13>

720 Yang, Y., Li, X., Cui, W., Zhou, S., Tan, R., & Wang, C. (2008). Structural stability and release
721 profiles of proteins from core-shell poly (DL-lactide) ultrafine fibers prepared by emulsion
722 electrospinning. *Journal of Biomedical Materials Research Part A*, 86A(2), 374–385.
723 <https://doi.org/10.1002/jbm.a.31595>

724 Yildiz, Z. I., Celebioglu, A., Kilic, M. E., Durgun, E., & Uyar, T. (2018). Menthol/cyclodextrin
725 inclusion complex nanofibers: Enhanced water-solubility and high-temperature stability of

726 menthol. *Journal of Food Engineering*, 224, 27–36.
727 <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JFOODENG.2017.12.020>

728 Zeng, J., Yang, L., Liang, Q., Zhang, X., Guan, H., Xu, X., ... Jing, X. (2005). Influence of the drug
729 compatibility with polymer solution on the release kinetics of electrospun fiber formulation.
730 *Journal of Controlled Release*, 105(1–2), 43–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jconrel.2005.02.024>

731 Zhang, B., Kang, F., Tarascon, J.-M., & Kim, J.-K. (2016). Recent advances in electrospun carbon
732 nanofibers and their application in electrochemical energy storage. *Progress in Materials*
733 *Science*, 76, 319–380. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.PMATSCI.2015.08.002>

734
735

736 **Figure Captions**

737

738 **Fig. 1.** Electrospun fibers developed: a) PLA; b) PLA-Cur; c) PLA/PVA-Cur; and d)
739 PLA.CNC/PVA-Cur.

740

741 **Fig. 2.** Scheme of the curcumin release process: concentration profiles and equilibrium for a)
742 PLA/PVA-Cur; and b) PLA.CNC/PVA-Cur mats.

743

744 **Fig. 3.** SEM micrographs at 5 and 10 kx and the fiber diameter distribution of electrospun
745 PLA mats: (a) PLA-Cur; (b) PLA/PVA-Cur; and (c) PLA.CNC/PVA-Cur,

746

747 **Fig. 4.** FTIR spectra of the PLA, curcumin and developed mats containing curcumin.

748

749 **Fig. 5.** X-ray diffraction patterns of electrospun mats and polymers PLA and PVA.

750

751 **Fig. 6.** DTG curves of: a) components; and b) active mats.

752

753 **Fig. 7.** Release kinetic of curcumin from uniaxial and coaxial electrospun mats to food
754 simulants: (a) 50% (v/v) ethanol and (b) 10% (v/v) ethanol.

755

756 Fig. 1

757

758

759 Fig. 2

760

761

762 Fig. 3

763

764

765

766 Fig. 4
767

768

769 Fig. 5

770

771

774 Fig. 7

775

776

777 Tables

778

779 **Table 1.** DSC parameters and crystallinity of the fibers during the first heating process.

Fibers	T_g (°C)	T_{cc} (°C)	T_{m1} (°C)	T_{m2} (°C)	X_{c, PLA}* (%)	X_{c, PVA}* (%)
PLA.CNC/PVA-Cur	53.3 ± 0.1 ^c	79.4 ± 0.3 ^b	145.4 ± 0.4 ^b	180.7 ± 0.8 ^b	3.3 ± 0.2 ^a	16.5 ± 2.4 ^a
PLA/PVA-Cur	54.3 ± 0.3 ^c	77.5 ± 0.6 ^a	145.8 ± 0.4 ^b	-	9.0 ± 0.5 ^c	-
PLA-Cur	54.7 ± 0.5 ^c	80.9 ± 0.6 ^b	149.2 ± 0.7 ^b	-	6.2 ± 0.5 ^b	-
PLA	40.2 ± 0.4 ^b	-	136.9 ± 3.3 ^a	147.3 ± 3.2 ^a	21.0 ± 1.7 ^d	-
PVA-Cur	36.1 ± 3.4 ^a	-	166.6 ± 3.8 ^c	204.1 ± 8.5 ^c	-	67.4 ± 3.6 ^c
PVA	40.2 ± 0.1 ^b	-	172.0 ± 0.1 ^d	200.7 ± 7.4 ^c	-	43.0 ± 9.5 ^b

780 *Crystallinity was calculated respect to melting heat of the 100% crystalline polymer, PLA
781 or PVA, according to crystalline phases presented in each case.

782 **Table 2.** TGA parameters and mass loss at maximum degradation rates.

Sample	$T_{\text{onset}} (^{\circ}\text{C})^{\text{a}*}$	$T_{\text{d,max1}}(^{\circ}\text{C})^{\text{b}*}$	$T_{\text{d,max2}}(^{\circ}\text{C})^{\text{b}*}$
PLA.CNC/PVA-Cur	302.1	333.2	443.5
PLA/PVA-Cur	305.7	340.3	439.0
PLA-Cur	325.5	353.6	-
PLA	296.0	331.5	-
PVA-Cur	298.5	333.7	441.6
PVA	292.6	330.4	445.3
Curcumin	272.2	309.3	390.0
CNC	289.6	293.6	353.8

783 ^{a*} T_{onset} is the temperature at 2.5% of weight loss.

784 ^{b*} $T_{\text{d,max1}}$ and $T_{\text{d,max2}}$ are the temperatures at the maximum degradation rates.

785 **Table 3.** Partition and diffusion coefficients and RMSE values of curcumin from electrospun
 786 materials into different food simulants at 40 °C.

Simulant	Electrospun mat	$K_{P,FS}$	D_p ($m^2 s^{-1}$)	RMSE
EtOH 10%	PLA-Cur	$6288^a \pm 30$	1.3×10^{-14}	0.15
	PLA/PVA-Cur	$10836^b \pm 40$	0.9×10^{-14}	0.22
	PLA.CNC/PVA-Cur	$10149^b \pm 25$	2.2×10^{-15}	0.18
EtOH 50%	PLA-Cur	$23^d \pm 3$	1.4×10^{-13}	0.10
	PLA/PVA-Cur	$349^c \pm 11$	1.1×10^{-14}	0.25
	PLA.CNC/PVA-Cur	$320^c \pm 5$	2.5×10^{-15}	0.44

787 a-d indicate significant differences on $K_{P,FS}$ values between mats and food simulants.